

USING SITUATION ASSIGNMENTS IN FORMING STUDENTS' CLINICAL THINKING.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8238598>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 31-July 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 05-August 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 11-August 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

medicine, thinking, clinical thinking, activity, process, modeling, imitation, problem situation, situational task, game, result.

ABSTRACT

In this article, the importance, forms and content of activities of situational tasks, role-playing and business games, which provide an opportunity to form the clinical thinking of students of higher medical institutions in the process of mastering the science of obstetrics and gynecology, are highlighted.

Enter. Currently, in the system of higher medical education, great attention is paid to the development and implementation of optimal teaching methods (diagnostics, treatment-prophylaxis and other problems) that will allow students not only to form deep theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications, but also to use them in practice in the future. Therefore, the main characteristic of a graduate of a medical university is the combination of professional competence and clinical thinking skills.

The formation of clinical thinking is considered a long-term process, and it is gradually developed during the study of obstetrics and gynecology by students.

The purpose of mastering this subject is to prepare physiological and complicated pregnant women for independent care, treatment, diagnosis, and prevention of postpartum complications; important gynecological diseases, emergency care at the pre-hospital stage, rehabilitation after pathological childbirth and gynecological diseases, and family planning and reproductive health protection measures.

At the same time, we help students understand the identified signs of pathology, put forward hypotheses about possible diseases; thinking in terms of forming a differential diagnosis and clinical diagnosis; determine the possible sequence of factors and situations that make up the etiology and pathogenesis of the disease; forecasting, making a treatment plan and evaluating its results; we should also include the skills of planning preventive and rehabilitation measures. Because the success of professional activities depends to a large extent on the manifestation of operational thinking based on clinical thinking.

Literature analysis. Scientific research related to the development of clinical thinking among students of medical institutions of higher education is conducted in the world's leading scientific centers and institutions of higher education, including Princeton University (USA),

Center of increasing to pedagogical qualification on the basis of Manchesters university (England), Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität It is conducted in Bonn (Germany), University of Strasbourg (France), Miyagi University of Education (Japan), Academy of Education (Russia), Bukhara State Medical Institute (Uzbekistan).

Russian scientists N.A. Ardamatsky, V.L. Bogdanovich, V.G. Vogralik, P.V. Kopnin, B.K. Lozovsky, I.E. Farber, S.P. Fedorov's studies have studied the conceptual basis of the content and manifestation of clinical thinking.

Uzbek scientists M.T.Khamdamova, G.N.Kurbanova, M.N.Batriddinova, K.I.Zhoraeva, Z.N.Boboeva and others in the direction of the formation, specific aspects, characteristics, and manifestations of professional, operative and clinical thinking conducted scientific research.

Foreign scientists R. Paul, N. N. Nepeivoda, D. Cluster, D. Halpern's work combines critical, operational and clinical thinking the possibilities of manifestation in the process of human activity are indicated.

The main part. In the educational process, it is appropriate to use educational and control situational tasks in order to choose research methods for forming the clinical thinking of students, differential diagnosis of diseases, and the use of adequate medical tactics.

Assignments are made taking into account the students' existing knowledge of the newly learned material and additional literature. It is also classified according to the course of study of students and is aimed at training doctors of various specialties (obstetrician-gynecologist, anesthesiologist-reanimatologist, surgeon, therapist, general practitioner).

During our pedagogical work at the Bukhara State Medical Institute, including the teaching of obstetrics and gynecology, we use several types of situational tasks.

First of all, these are tasks aimed at solving typical specific situations that require a short and clear answer, aimed at developing and strengthening obstetric knowledge among students.

The second type of tasks are more complex clinical tasks that require sufficient theoretical knowledge and contain a lot of information, which can be solved by different approaches.

These types of clinical tasks allow to develop the student's clinical thinking, his ability to make quick decisions in clinical situations and choose the right medical tactics.

The third type of situations has an extended logical structure and includes tasks consisting of programmed learning and control elements.

These situational assignments provide an opportunity for students to develop clinical and logical thinking in the diagnosis process and require fundamental knowledge of Obstetrics and Gynecology.

Solving situational tasks also provides an opportunity to form creative abilities in the personality of students. On this basis, constantly searching for new solutions, justifying them, summarizing and systematizing the acquired knowledge, transferring them to non-standard situations makes knowledge more flexible and mobile, develops skills and abilities, increases the need for self-education, develops the logical component of clinical thinking.

Organizational-active, role-playing and business games are also actively and effectively used in the process of organizing educational activities in the field of "obstetrics and gynecology".

Organizational-active games ensure the organization of collective mental activity of students based on the interaction of all students in the group in the process of developing a problem situation and analyzing it while maintaining the personal position of each.

Role-playing games are characterized by the fact that students are given a specific task or problem and the roles in solving it are distributed among the participants.

Business and business games are organized according to the nature of decisions and actions taken in strict accordance with the next events with the dynamic development of the situation, task or problem as a method of teaching professional activity by modeling close to real conditions. Business games are a form of re-creating the subject or social content of professional activity, modeling the system of relationships specific to this type of practice. The purpose of the game is to develop the activity of its participants in a special (game-like) simulation model.

These games use actual, realistic, typical, complete, uplifting and developmental situations.

During the educational process, we offered several variants of clinical games depending on the level of difficulty.

The first option is "doctor-patient". In this, the conditions of the doctor's intellectual professional activity aimed at identifying diseases and treating the patient are modeled. This form of the game is organized in the range of game activity of one student and a whole group of students together with the teacher.

The second option is "Consilium", in addition to the treating doctor, consultants are involved in the game, and therefore different players play the role of doctors of different specialties and levels of training.

The third variant of the clinical game is called Ward Doctor, as the ward doctor examines and supervises several patients on a daily basis, in order to model a real situation, students play the role of patients at different stages of examination, disease and treatment.

One of the most difficult and complex business games is "Women's advice" - "Perinatal hospital". because the organization of these games includes not only a clinical but also an organizational aspect.

Summary. In our country, great attention is paid to the rapid development of the social sphere, strengthening the health of the population, and developing effective mechanisms for the training of future medical workers. Development of professional knowledge, skills and thinking of future specialists on the basis of modern technologies, formation of innovative thinking and potential in them is gaining importance in teaching the science of gynecology.

From this point of view, as a result of the application of imitation modeling methods in the educational process, not only the formation and improvement of academic, social, personal, professional competences of students, but also the development of clinical thinking, which allows for correct diagnosis, differential diagnosis, the selection of the best tactics of clinically similar diseases, management, treatment, emergency medical assistance will be available.

References:

1. Абдуллаев К. Ф., Бобомуродова Н. Д. Didaktik talim vositalari talim jarayoni samaradorligini taminlash omili sifatida: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.53885/edinres.2022.55.50.016> //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 3. – С. 81-86.
2. Буравкова, А. Г. Ситуационные задачи как способ формирования клинического мышления врача / А. Г. Буравкова, О. Б. Демьянова // Личность, семья и общество: вопросы педагогики и психологии. – 2014. – № 38. – С. 41–45.
3. Курбанова Г.Н. Талабалар касбий тафаккурини ривожлантиришда замонавий

- маъруза машғулотларининг аҳамияти // Биология и интегративная медицина. 2021. №2 (49).
4. Петров, В. И. Клиническое мышление в современной системе высшего медицинского образования в России / В. И. Петров, М. Ю. Фролов // Мед. образование и профессиональное развитие. – 2010. – № 1. – С. 59–62
5. Хамдамова М.Т., Уринова Ш.А. Тиббиёт олий таълим муассасалари талабаларида гинекология фанини ўқитиш жараёнида клиник тафаккурни ривожлантириш тузилмаси // Биология и интегративная медицина. 2022. №1 (54).
6. Хурса, Р. В. О клиническом мышлении и преподавании клинических дисциплин / Р. В. Хурса // Мед. журн. – 2004 – С. 106–108.
7. Mirzaeva, A. S. (2022). INTRA-LINGUISTIC AND EXTRA-LINGUISTIC FACTORS RELATED TO THE LANGUAGE AND VOCABULARY OF THE BASIC CONCEPTS OF RENAISSANCE ENGLISH PHILOSOPHY. Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture, 1(5), 9-17.
8. Aziza, M. (2022). THE THEORY OF INTERTEXTUALITY AS A PARADIGM AND THE IMPACT OF THIS THEORY ON TRANSLATION. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2(5), 990-995.
9. Мирзаева, А. Ш. (2021). РЕМИНИСЦЕНЦИЯ КАК ЭЛЕМЕНТ ИНТЕРТЕКСТУАЛЬНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИИ РИКА РИОРДАНА "PERCY JACKSON AND THE LIGHTNING THIEF". МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА, 4(3).
10. Mirzaeva, A. S. (2022). THEORY IN INTERTEXTUALITY AND THREE SEAMLESS INTERTEXTS: M. BUTTERFLY BY DAVID H. HWANG, AS IS BY WILLIAM M. HOFFMAN, AND EXECUTION OF JUSTICE BY EMILY MANN. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(5-2), 160-165.
11. Shavkatovna, M. A. (2022). ENLIGHTENMENT-MORAL, PHILOSOPHICAL, LINGUISTIC VIEWS OF MODERN CREATORS.
12. Shavkatovna, M. A. . (2022). Interrextuality in Rick Riordan's Work. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(9), 180–185. Retrieved from <https://www.grnjournals.us/index.php/ajshr/article/view/1507>.
13. Mirzaeva Aziza Shavkatovna. (2021). Allusion As The Way Of Rendering Elements Of Ancient Greek Mythology In The Tissue Of Modern Literature. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 3(01), 505-514. <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajssei/Volume03Issue01-91>
14. Shavkatovna, M. A. . (2022). Interrextuality in Rick Riordan's Work. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(9), 180–185. Retrieved from <https://www.grnjournals.us/index.php/ajshr/article/view/1507>
15. 15 Aziza Mirzaeva Shavkatovna. (2022). THE INTERTEXTUAL AND INTERCULTURAL REFERENCES IN LODGE'S CAMPUS NOVELS. American Journal Of Philological Sciences, 2(11), 29–35. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajps/Volume02Issue11-05>
16. Aziza, M. (2022). THE THEORY OF INTERTEXTUALITY AS A PARADIGM AND THE IMPACT OF THIS THEORY ON TRANSLATION.
17. Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich Shodiev. Bakaev Najmiddin Bakaevich. expressions.. (2020). The role of the Latin language in the history of world statehood. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 05 (85), 367-372. Soi: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1/TAS-05-85-71> Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS> Scopus ASCC: 1203. THE ROLE OF THE LATIN LANGUAGE

IN THE HISTORY OF WORLD STATEHOOD

18. Islam in the evolution of social and political views of the Uzbek Jadids, their role in the formation of the idea of National Independence KB Shadmanov, SS Shodiev, TN Zayniddinovna
CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY 2 (2), 44-50 2021

19. Shodiyev Shaxobiddin Sharofiddinovich, & Tasheva Nafisa Zayniddinovna. (2021). THE ROLE OF THE WAY OF THE GREAT STEPPE IN THE CONTINUITY AND RELATIONSHIP OF THE PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE OF THE MUSLIM EAST AND THE RENAISSANCE WEST. Innovative Academy Research Support Center, 1(3), 9–13.
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4925956>

20. Shodiev Shahobiddin Sharofiddinovich, & Majitova Nafisa Zokirovna. (2021). IDEAS ABOUT AN IDEAL PERSON, LANGUAGE, PROSPERITY IN THE EVOLUTION OF PUBLIC AND POLITICAL VIEWS OF THE UZBEK JADIDS OF THE BEGINNING OF THE XX CENTURY. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 1(3), 5–8. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4925897>

21. Shodiev Sh.Sh., Majitova N.Z. Ideas About an Ideal Person, Language, Prosperity in the Evolution of Public and Political Views of the Uzbek Jadids of the Beginning of the XX century // Euroasian Journal of Academic Research. V.1 Iss.03.- 2021.P. 5-8.

22. Shodiev Sh.Sh., Tasheva N.Z. The Role of the way of the Great Steppe in the continuity and relationship of the philosophy and culture of the Muslim East and the Renaissance West // Euroasian Journal of Academic Research. V.1 Iss.03.- 2021. P.9-13.

23. Shodiev Sh.Sh., Hakimova M.A. Revenge idea's transformation in "Hamlet" poem // Euroasian Journal of Academic Research. V.1 Iss.03.- 2021. P. 53-55.

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